

115966 – PREFER

Patient Preferences in Benefit-Risk Assessments during the Drug Life Cycle

WP4 – Recommendations

Summary report on training materials (D4.5)

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Abstract

Patients' preferences are a growing topic of interest, and stakeholders (e.g. regulators, payers, industry, and patient organizations) have called for greater involvement of patients. The objective of PREFER is to guide industry, regulatory authorities and HTA bodies and reimbursement agencies on how patient preferences can be assessed and used to inform medical product decision making by developing expert and evidence-based recommendations.

Among the diverse outputs of the project, PREFER developed training material as defined by a set of webinars to further assist in the development and execution of patient preference studies. The webinars, hosted by PREFER, share results and lessons learned from conducting patient preference studies within the project. Much of the information presented in these webinars has been published in peer reviewed literature, a list of publications can be found:

a) <https://www.imi-prefer.eu/publications/>

b) https://explore.openaire.eu/search/advanced/research-outcomes?f0=relprojectid&fv0=corda_h2020::42695dacf04480f35d6e4c046353a580&type=publications&qf=false&sortBy=resultdateofacceptance_descending

Webinars listed below are available in the PREFER YouTube playlist. Most of the slides of these webinar are also available. Links to these slides can be found in the description to the video on YouTube:

https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLN-kgkHBHa25apivf7wlwqNv5HiVX_VCZ

Training material

Title	Description	Link
Patient preferences in drug development and evaluation	This webinar provides results from research conducted within the PREFER project on the value of patient preference studies for different stakeholders, including regulatory agencies and HTA bodies and payers. The webinar concludes with a summary of identified stakeholder needs based on a series of interviews conducted by PREFER project members.	https://youtu.be/JH9cBe2tifQ
Patient involvement in patient preference studies	Patients are key in the success of patient preference studies. This webinar focuses on the role of patients as partners in patient preference studies. We explain the value of involving patients at the stages of design and conduct of a patient preference study as well as at the level of communication.	https://youtu.be/9SfvcHDV3w8
The PREFER Research Agenda: Identifying Methodological Priorities for Patient Preferences Research Using Stakeholder Input	In this webinar the research agenda from PREFER is outlined, including the identification of more promising methods and corresponding methodological questions to provide an overview of the research questions that are being addressed as a part of the PREFER case studies to identify future research opportunities based on questions not explored in PREFER case studies.	https://youtu.be/j8DKk_8G7RI
Designing, conducting and applying results from patient preference studies: the PREFER framework	Incorporating patient preferences into decision-making is an important part of patient-focused drug development. The lack of a clear, practical framework for measuring patient preferences was one of stakeholders' main concerns brought up during PREFER's initial research. This webinar will introduce the PREFER framework for patient preference studies, with a particular focus on points to consider for method selection and the application of preference study results to inform regulatory and HTA decision-making.	https://youtu.be/QFif9UPQkw
Patient preferences to Assess Value IN Gene therapies: the PAVING study as IMI PREFER case study	Gene therapies are innovative therapies that are increasingly being developed. However, health technology assessment and payer decision-making on these therapies is impeded by uncertainties. Through measuring patient preferences regarding gene therapies, the importance of unique elements beyond health gain can be quantified and inform value assessments. Therefore, the Patient preferences to Assess Value IN Gene therapies (PAVING) study was conducted to investigate treatment attributes important to hemophilia patients and the trade-offs they are willing to make when asked to choose between a standard of care and gene therapy. During this webinar, insights will be shared on how a patient preference study was designed in the complex context of gene therapies, as well as the results and their potential impact.	https://youtu.be/6lOnWwLv5Vg
The importance of different symptoms to people living with Chronic	Understanding the needs and preferences of patients in relation to their disease symptoms is key to the design of clinical trials for new therapies which address what matters most to patients. This webinar will present the design and results of a patient preference study with COPD patients in five	https://youtu.be/-NsE1SuUysQ

<p>Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD): results of a multi-country patient preference study</p>	<p>countries, to understand the importance they place on different disease symptoms. We show how patient preference studies, conducted early in the product lifecycle and with a focus on different symptom-based health states, can help to inform the selection of endpoints for patient-centric clinical trials.</p>	
<p>Patient Preferences in Rheumatoid Arthritis</p>	<p>Rheumatoid arthritis (sometimes called “RA”) is a long-term condition that mainly affects the joints and causes pain, swelling, stiffness and often fatigue. RA is fairly common and affects around 1% of the population. In most cases, patients begin having symptoms between 40 to 60 years of age, but it can also begin earlier, or later in life. During the webinar, insights will be shared on two patient preference studies focusing on treatments for RA and treatments to prevent RA. Their design, the results, potential impact and how we worked with patient research partners to develop these studies and the impact of the collaboration.</p>	<p>https://youtu.be/EjbHN_VqbD4</p>
<p>Patient Preferences for Non-Small-Cell Lung Cancer Treatment Options</p>	<p>In the treatment paradigm for Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer (NSCLC), patients and clinicians have to face a choice between a more aggressive treatment with a greater impact on the quality of life versus an alternative that may be less effective but that carries fewer side effects.</p> <p>One of PREFER’s core case studies explored patient preferences for lung cancer treatments, assessing which trade-offs between benefit and risks related to treatment alternatives that patients are willing to accept or not. In this webinar, we will provide a brief explanation of the disease and the decision-making sensitive situation, how the patient preference study was designed and its main results. We will then discuss what implications the results may have and the lessons learned in conducting the study.</p>	<p>https://youtu.be/1T9bpr3B06A</p>
<p>Patient Preferences for Antithrombotic Treatment in Acute and Chronic Phases of Myocardial Infarction</p>	<p>Antithrombotic treatments are used to prevent the risk of future ischemic events in patients following a myocardial infarction (heart attack). These drugs can be administered during emergency medical care in a hospital or after leaving the hospital when the patients’ condition is more stable. This webinar describes a study, conducted in collaboration with the IMI PREFER consortium, that aimed to understand patient preferences for benefits and risks for antithrombotic treatment throughout the acute and chronic stages of heart disease.</p> <p>In this webinar, we will describe how the patient preference study was designed and its main results. We will then discuss what implications the results may have on the development of drugs to treat heart disease. Finally, we will show how the preference data may be combined with clinical data (trial data and real-world data) to understand how the treatment’s benefit-risk profile may be expected to vary in the real-world target population.</p>	<p>https://youtu.be/1ohRvrn9O0</p>
<p>Areas of Future Research in Patient Preferences</p>	<p>The PREFER project explored methodological questions that were considered higher priority based on discussion and ranking among stakeholders, however, we could not explore all research questions given the constraints of a 5-year time</p>	<p>https://youtu.be/9UElyR2nA7E</p>

	period and a finite number of case studies. This session will review topics for future research.	
Methods for patient preference studies: what to use when	In the PREFER project case studies different methods were used for eliciting preferences. This session will focus on what methods to use when for the different MPLC decision-points based on criteria that were found important to select methods and we compare the methods based on the obtained outcomes in the case studies.	https://youtu.be/KC7kKUu7QM4
Patient Preferences for the Treatment of Chronic Pain: Results and Methodological Insights from an Industry Case Study	Osteoarthritis (OA) and Chronic Low Back Pain (CLBP) are two of the most common chronic pain conditions worldwide. Both conditions are associated with substantial humanistic and socioeconomic burdens. There is an unmet need for novel, nonopioid treatments for the management of chronic pain conditions because available therapies often have limited effect or work for only some patients. To quantify patients' perspectives on this unmet need, Pfizer and Lilly conducted a patient preference study in the US and UK. The study team conducted a number comparisons of different methods of preference elicitation (discrete-choice experiments and object-case best-worst scaling) and analysis (random parameters logit and latent class analysis) and compared results across countries. In this webinar, the study team will describe the results of the study and the insights contribute to the final PREFER recommendations.	https://youtu.be/moq8CRXaHGQ
Case study: Multiple Myeloma (Use actual title from case study.)	Presenting the results of a Multiple Myeloma (MM) patient preference study that aimed to understand the unmet needs, treatment outcomes and attributes (side-effects, symptoms, efficacy outcomes) that are most important to MM patients. What were the methodologies (patient discussions, online survey methods) that were used, how patients and patients' organizations contributed to the design and conduct of our study, and how the results can inform decision-making across the medicinal product life cycle, such as: industry in selecting clinical trial endpoints, regulators when assessing benefits and risks and HTA bodies for informing reimbursement of Multiple Myeloma treatments.	https://youtu.be/a1ThMqz_HtY
Case study: Diabetes Mellitus (Use actual title from case study.)	Exploring the results of the diabetes patient preference study. And discuss whether outcomes differ depending on what type of preference elicitation method is used, what kind of educational tool patients are presented with, the way patients are recruited, and patient characteristics/experiences.	https://youtu.be/uMHlzNC6ZX0
PREFER recommendations on the use of patient preference studies	Presentation of the key recommendations from PREFER.	https://youtu.be/xqJiAUC4eSg
EMA Qualification Opinion	In this webinar we explain the key findings from the process and potential future implications of the EMA Qualification Opinion.	https://youtu.be/KqQG9IFh8r4